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ABSTRACT

This study identifies education as a factor which manipulates the rural to urban migration observed in the particular areas of the city of Chennai, Madurai and Bangalore and need for the enactment of new education policy. The research was conducted in the same cities because the influence of education from rural-urban in some selected areas can be observed. It was carried out in Madurai, Chennai and Bangalore. Data was gathered by using online interview techniques so that correct and authentic information from the concerned people should be collected. The study reveals that education is the major factor prevailing in today's society and major pros and cons of the establishment of New Education Policy. The major objectives of the paper are to understand the awareness, perception and impacts of the New Educational Policy of 2020 and To know about the prevailing situation of the Educational policy for determining the practical implications in providing adequate trained staff and resources.

Keywords: Education System, Urban, Social Status, Education, Policy, Complexity, New Educational Policy - India

INTRODUCTION

Our country has been under the clutches of a stringent education system, for almost the past 34 years, which has hampered the growth of many renowned persons in the society. To change the Root System of education and bring out a more practical way of teaching and learning a New Education Policy is brought. It is a step towards a New Education Policy and is built upon the foundational pillars of Access, Equity, Quality, Affordability and Accountability and shall prove to be efficient enough. Evolution of the New Education Policy' under the authority of T.S.R. Subramanian, took shape back in May, 2016 and the entire concept of building a Holistic education approach comes into existence. After the 2019 Lok Sabha elections the Draft National Education Policy, 2019 was made public and opened for feedback and reviews. After due consideration of the opinions and feedback of nearly over 2 lakh out of 2.5 lakh Gram Panchayats, 6600 Blocks, 6000 ULBs, 676 Districts, the NEP, 2020 took shape. The key highlights of the New Education Policy, 2020 is based on the 5+3+3+4 structure of education with curriculum structure corresponding to ages 3-8, 8-11, 11-14, and 14-18 years respectively. The NEP 2020 aims at making "India a global knowledge superpower". This is a landmark change by the Indian Government, as they have replaced the 34-year-old National Policy on Education, which was framed in 1986, with the New Education Policy of 2020. The NEP, which has been approved by the union cabinet, has made revolutionary reforms in the Indian education paradigm. This is a landmark change by the Indian Government, as they have replaced the 34-year-old National Policy on Education, which was framed in 1986, with the New Education Policy of 2020. The NEP, which has been approved by the union cabinet, has made revolutionary reforms in the Indian education paradigm. The recognition of the importance of life skills was long overdue, and the NEP has given more attention to developing life skills in the educational process. Quality of teaching is one of the primary agendas of the policy as well. Teachers are integral to the education system, and without improving the way teachers are trained, it will be difficult to improve the quality of education. The main aim of the paper is to analyse the scope of NEP-2020 and the problems in implementations.

Objectives

- To understand about the impacts of the New Educational Policy of 2020
- To know about the prevailing situation of the Educational policy.
- To determine the practical implications to provide adequate trained staff and resources
- To know about the opinion of academicians and the politicians towards the new educational policy 2020.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant association between the age and the preference to rate that the populations were aware about the New Education Policy of 2020.

H1: There is a significant association between the age and the preference to rate that the populations were aware about the New Education Policy of 2020.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The various merits of the higher educational policies in the NEP, 2020 such as the Student Centric Model, Competency based Continuous Evaluation System, Research and Innovation focused, Improved STEM model of the HE curriculum, Merit based Student admissions, Faculty Selection & Promotion and the researcher also further suggested few ideas for improvements. (Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, Shubhrajyotsna 2020) At the university/HEI level, no single stream/discipline university shall remain in existence but transformed into multidisciplinary, holistic delivery systems. A single nomenclature, "University," shall prevail and also criticised about the implementation by Strengthening Central Advisory Board of Education, Redesignation of MHRD as Ministry of Education and Financial and other infrastructural support. (Darolia, R., Koedel, C., Main, J. B., Ndashimye, J. F., & Yan, J. 2020) The STEM enrollment's access to high school math and science course's effects were identified by plausibly exogenous variation in course offerings. (Ball, 2019) The Australian education policy as a case of global educational reform activity covering range of points which exemplifies aspects of current assemblage of global education reform activity. The study considers assessment policies and contradictions between learning and assessments and implications of that for professional development of teachers. (Mridul Madhav Panditrao., & Minnu Mridul Panditrao 2020). The Boost of GER through Autonomy to the Private Sector. Quality education to everyone is one of the major goals of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal. The private sector should give 20% free seats, 30% half fee scholarships so that many poor but merit-based students get free or discounted fee study opportunities which is based on the NEP-2020. (Aithal, P. S. & Suresh Kumar, P.M. 2016). The free education at HE level will boost GER of higher education in the country by allocating free merit-based seats for merit-based students which is an important highlight of NEP-2020. (Singh, J. D. 2011). The Accreditation Council. The NEP-2020 has established the Control of Quality through Biennial Accreditation Process. The quality of education is currently monitored by the National Assessment and Accreditation Council and awards the graded accreditations to HEIs. This accreditation timeframe is five years. Due to the short timeframe reason, HEIs are not continuously monitored for their accreditation status. (Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T. & Suresh Kumar, P. M. 2016). For the better quality work and performance it is mandatory to opt biennial accreditation. To make accreditation status more serious and effective for continuous improvement, NEP-2020 has simplified it and made it mandatory as a biennial accreditation process. (Ulker, N., & Bakioglu, A. 2019). The use of Information Communication and Computation Technologies (ICCT) including Education technology, Internet technology, Artificial intelligence, Virtual reality, etc are very essential in effective implementation of education in the 21st century. (Aithal, P. S., & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, 2015). The characteristics of the ideal education system and also to enhance GER by opting the latest technologies to help in the planning, design offering effective online education to realize the importance. (Aithal, P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, 2016). Due to improved tech generations, technology driven education is going to replace classroom based education and the policies of NEP-2020. (Suresh Kumar, P. M. & Aithal, P. S. 2016). It is expected that during the 21st century that laying the foundation for online based but also supports classroom based education system by adding more research components in it. (Ossiannilsson, E., Altinay, F., & Altinay, Z. 2016). The Integrated Controlling & Monitoring System of the educational sector and institutions both primary and higher education. The implementation process is divided into seven stages. As per NEP-2020, the first 10 years is the implementation period and the next 10 years is the operational period. (National Education Policy 2020). The most important for education leaders are Self-contribution to research and innovation. New researchers get inspiration by seeing the contribution of leaders to perform better thus Education Leaders should be Role-Models. (Aithal P. S. 2018). The HEIs should cultivate role models in this sector who should be super performers to the IPR of the organization so that the organization can prove that higher contribution is possible. (Aithal, P. S., 2016). The Professors who hold administrative positions are also expected to research and publish in their leisure period to be role models to young researchers. (Speizer, J. J. 1981). The importance of student admission based on merit by giving importance to social justice. He also comments that

the quality of higher education and research can be improved only if all faculty selections and promotions are merit based. (Sabic-El-Rayess, A. 2016). All kinds of reservations and lobbies should be curbed at individual institution level by means of appointing highly qualified and proven leaders as members of the Board of Governors. (Nyden, P. 2003). The affirmative actions based appointments is not a solution and the reservation system should be diminishing rather than expanding to more people as it negatively impacts the meritorious students and the fair opportunities are being questioned. (Gopalan, 2020). The Merit based Student admissions, Faculty Selection & Promotion also stresses that merit-based appointments are essential at all policy formulating and regulating levels of HE Councils. (Aithal, P. S. 2015). The Higher education institutions which have the autonomy to do innovations in deciding the courses, curriculum, pedagogy, examination and evaluation could improve the quality of education offered by them. (Benjamin, E. 1994). In the university affiliation system, affiliated institutions do not have any autonomy in teaching-learning and evaluation systems thereby the quality and motivation of both students and faculty members get affected. (Sankaran, K., & Joshi, G. V. 2016). The current teacher centric model where the teachers decide the subjects, curriculum, evaluation, etc will be replaced by the student centric model where the student gets right to decide the subject he has to study from the institution. (Simão, A. M. V., & Flores, M. A. 2010)

Research Questions

The research questions were,

1. Are you aware of the New Education Policy (NEP) of 2020?
2. How do you agree with the new changes that were brought up in education?
3. Is it easy to bring about sudden changes in the educational level without adequate trained staff and resources?
4. Does this new changes in education could bring out many practical implications and challenges
5. In what percentage is it practically possible to implement sudden changes in education particularly in rural parts of India?

Research Design

The researcher obtained the primary source of data by conducting an empirical study on seeking responses from the general public based on a questionnaire and also relied on secondary sources of data such as books, journals, e-sources, articles and newspapers. The research method followed here is empirical research.

Participants

A total of 200 samples have been taken out of which is taken through convenient sampling methods. The sample frames taken by the researcher are various students and their parents especially belonging to the rural parts of Madurai, Chennai and Bangalore. The independent variables are age, gender and occupation.

Data Collection tools

The data from the participants were collected via Google Forms as the COVID-19 lockdown norms were in place. Once the data was collected it was analyzed using the SPSS. The statistical tool used by the researcher is graphical representation.

RESULTS

Results are presented under each related chart as follows:

GENDER FREQUENCY CHART 1

With respect to the current survey results, the frequency chart 1 is created out of the survey responses received from several people. The present frequency table is based on the gender of persons who were taken as samples. Among the samples, the numbers of female responses are comparatively more when compared to the number of responses by male samples. Where the sample response from females is 111 (55.5%) and the response from male is 89 (44.5%) in number. Thus, on the whole there were about 200 samples taken for the present survey.

AGE FREQUENCY CHART 2

With respect to the current survey results, the frequency chart 2 is created out of the survey responses received from several people. The present frequency table is based on the age of the persons. Among the persons who are between 15-25, there were 75 (37.5%) sample responses taken and between the 26-35, there were about 34 (17%) sample responses taken. Between those who were between 36-45 there were 74 (37%) sample responses taken and between those who are 46 & above, there were 17 (8.5%) sample responses for this survey. Thus, on the whole there were about 200 samples taken for the present survey.

OCCUPATIONAL FREQUENCY CHART 3

With respect to the current survey results, the frequency chart 3 is created out of the survey responses received from several people. The present frequency table is based on occupation of the persons. Among the persons who are students, there were 68 (34%) sample responses taken and among the public sector, there were about 35 (17.5%) sample responses taken. Among those who have a private sector there were 36 (18%) sample responses taken and among those who have their own business, there were 30 (15%) sample responses taken and among those who are unemployed, there were 21 (10.5%) sample responses for this survey. Thus, on the whole there were about 200 samples taken for the present survey.

Question 1: Are you aware of the New Education Policy (NEP) of 2020?

GRAPH 1

Results:

From the survey : in graph 1, it is observed that it exhibits the age distribution of the respondents among different genders of the respondents and their opinion on the criteria whether they are aware of the New Education Policy (NEP) of 2020. The maximum number of responses was collected from both the male and female respondents who are between age groups of 15-25 and 26-35.

Question 2: How do you agree with the new changes that were brought up in education?

GRAPH 2

Results

From the survey : in graph 2, it is observed that it exhibits the occupational distribution of the respondents among different genders of the respondents and their opinion on the criteria of how people agree with the new changes that were brought up in education. The maximum number of responses were collected from both the male and female respondents who are working in both public and private sectors.

Question 3: Is it easy to bring about sudden changes in the educational level without adequate trained staff and resources?

GRAPH 3

Results

From the survey : in graph 3, it is observed that it exhibits the age distribution of the respondents among different genders of the respondents and their opinion on the criteria whether it is easy to bring about sudden changes in the educational level without adequate trained staff and resources. The maximum number of responses were collected from both the male and female respondents who are between age groups of 15-25 and 26-35.

Question 4: Does this new changes in education could bring out many practical implications and challenges

GRAPH 4

Results

From the survey : in graph 4, it is observed that it exhibits the occupational distribution of the respondents among different genders of the respondents and their opinion on the criteria does this new changes in the education could bring out many practical implications and challenges. The maximum number of responses were collected from the male agrees that it is difficult to bring out many practical implications and challenges in the implementation of the NEP.

Question 5: In what percentage is it practically possible to implement sudden changes in education particularly in rural parts of India?

GRAPH 5

Results

From the survey : in graph 5, it is observed that it exhibits the age distribution of the respondents among different genders of the respondents and their opinion on the criteria in what percentage it is practically possible to implement sudden changes in the education particularly in rural parts of India. The maximum number of responses were collected from both the male and female respondents who are between age groups of 15-25 and 26-35.

DISCUSSION

It exhibits the age distribution of the respondents among different genders of the respondents and their opinion of the criteria whether they are forced to migrate to cities in order to pursue higher education. The maximum number of responses were collected from both the male and female respondents who are between age groups of 15-25 and 26-35. The main reason behind this awareness among the higher education department is that because the students are still being very much part of the education system is due to the government had envisioned for millions of students (Graph 1). It exhibits the occupational distribution of the respondents among different genders of the respondents and their opinion on the criteria of how people agree with the new changes that were brought up in education. The maximum number of responses were collected from both the male and female respondents who are working in both public and private sectors. The main reason behind why students strongly disagree is the new regulations and changes brought by the new educational policies since they were following a different existing educational policy for the past 34 years since 1986 and it's not possible to opt for a new policy overnight (Graph 2). It exhibits the age distribution of the respondents among different genders of the respondents and their opinion on the criteria whether it is easy to bring about sudden changes in the educational level without adequate trained staff and resources. The maximum numbers of responses were collected from both the male and female respondents who are between age groups of 15-25 and 26-35. The main reason behind why the respondents disagree and claim that it is not possible to make sudden

changes in the educational level without adequate trained staff and resources is that there is a lack of trained staff to meet the new conditions and needs of the NEP-2020 (Graph 3). It exhibits the occupational distribution of the respondents among Different genders of the respondents and their opinion on the criteria does this new changes in the education could bring out many practical implications and challenges. The maximum number of responses collected from the male agrees that it is difficult to bring out many practical implications and challenges in the implementation of the NEP. The main reason behind why the maximum response recorded by the both public and private sector respondents is that there are many practical implications and challenges to meet the objectives of the new legislation on the education cause there's an alarming demand for the implications due to insufficient resources (Graph 4). It exhibits the age distribution of the respondents among different genders of the respondents and their opinion on the criteria in what percentage it is practically possible to implement sudden changes in the education particularly in rural parts of India. The maximum numbers of responses were collected from both the male and female respondents who are between age groups of 15-25 and 26-35. The main reason behind the lower implications in the rural areas is that in comparison with urban areas, rural areas lag in providing all basic commodities in education and other resources (Graph5).

CONCLUSION

Advanced education is a significant angle in choosing the economy, societal position, innovation reception, and solid human conduct in each nation. Improving GER to remember each resident of the nation for advanced education contributions is the obligation of the instruction branch of the nation government. Public Training Strategy of India 2020 is walking towards accomplishing such target by making creative strategies to improve the quality, allure, reasonableness, and expanding the stock by opening up the advanced education for the private area and simultaneously with severe controls to keep up quality in each advanced education organization. By empowering merit-based confirmations with free-ships and grants, merit and exploration based persistent entertainers as employees, and legitimacy based demonstrated pioneers in managing bodies, and severe observing of value through biennial accreditation dependent on self-statement of progress through innovation based checking, NEP-2020 is relied upon to satisfy its destinations by 2030. All advanced education establishments with current classification of associated schools will extend as multi-disciplinary independent schools with degree giving force in their name or becomes constituent schools of their subsidiary colleges. An unbiased office Public Exploration Establishment will subsidize for creative undertakings in need research regions of fundamental sciences, applied sciences, and sociologies and humanities. HE framework will change itself as understudy driven with the opportunity to pick center and unified subjects inside an order and across disciplines. Employees additionally get self-governance to pick educational plan, technique, teaching method and assessment models inside the given strategy structure. These changes will begin from the scholastic year 2021-22 and will proceed until the year 2030 where the main degree of change is required to noticeable. Subsequently, the Indian advanced education framework is moving from educator driven to understudy driven, data driven to information driven, marks driven to abilities driven, assessment driven to exploratory driven, learning driven to investigate driven, and decision driven to competency driven. From the above analysis, it is evident that the null hypothesis has been rejected and the alternate hypothesis has been proved, there is a significant association between the age and the preference to rate that the populations were aware about the New Education Policy of 2020.

LIMITATIONS

The Major limitation of the study is the sample frame. The sample frame Collected via online platforms and that is the limitation of the study, the real field experience is missed out due to the pandemic. The restrictive area of sample size is yet another drawback of the research; collection of data via online platforms is limiting the researcher to collect data from the field. Since the data is collected on an online platform wherein the respondent is not known, the original opinion of the respondent is not found, the researcher could only come to an approximate conclusion of what the respondent is feeling to convey.

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